

Universität Potsdam

Confirmation of withdrawal from the PROTEST-AIRT project

Marie Skłodowska-Curie Postdoctoral Fellowship (Grant Agreement 101057156)

Dear Participant,

Thank you for your interest in this research project. Hereby I confirm your withdrawal from the PROTEST-AIRT project and inform you that any information related to you has been deleted or destroyed, including audio recordings, photographs, your ‘protest diary’ as well as your contact information. The data was destroyed at this date: _____.

I remind you that there are no consequences of any kind because of your withdrawal from this study. If you are still interested in the preliminary findings of the PROTEST-AIRT project, please visit the website: www.uni-potsdam.de/en/protest-airt

Please contact me again if you have any additional questions or concerns. For any data concerns, you can contact the Data Protection Officer, [ADD FULL NAME]: [ADD EMAIL]

Thank you for your collaboration,

Dr Alexander ARAYA LÓPEZ
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